

Outcome of Case Study:

After applying the HARMLESS DSS, a preferable SSbD version within the design space could be successfully identified. However, benefits are limited by the performance that does not reach the benchmark, making the project likely to not proceed further to pilot phase. More details in the next episode!

References

To see the full references, scan the QR code:

Partners involved: **BASF (as main contributor)**

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HARMLESS

Oxide-perovskites for automotive catalysts

Advanced High Aspect Ratio and Multicomponent materials: towards comprehensive intelligent Testing and Safe by design Strategies

www.harmless-project.eu

HARMLESS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 953183.

Material: Oxide-perovskites ($\text{La}_x\text{Co}/\text{Ni}_x\text{O}_3$)

The oxide-perovskites investigated by HARMLESS are advanced, nano enabled materials which consist of particles (black powder at the macroscopic level). Their functionality is enabled by their multicomponent structure, characterized by multiple metal ions arranged ideally in a cubic crystal lattice.

Functionality and application

Removal of pollutants generated upon combustion in automotive engines: they reduce NO and oxidize CO and hydrocarbons, in a narrow window of air-to-fuel ratio, buffering lean/rich fluctuations.

Objective of the Case Study

Following a **Safe and Sustainable by Design Innovation approach**, six different oxide perovskite versions were synthesized by BASF R&D, to find the best compromise between performance, safety and sustainability aspects.

Design space

The amount of Cobalt, Nickel and dopants (Palladium or Platinum) is tailored by synthesis and modulate their performance.

Innovation in industry

Oxide-perovskites' **SSbD screening** was done in the **HARMLESS Decision Support System (DSS)** starting from ideation to lab phase.

Benefits of the Case Study

Positive impact to SDG 11 (target 11.6) improving air quality and waste in cities.

Target 11.6: By 2030, reduce the adverse per capita environmental impact of cities, including by paying special attention to air quality and municipal and other waste management.

User testimonials / Call to action:

Simple, TRL adapted and compact e-platform

Best suited for startups & SMEs which can't afford high product stewardship costs at early stages

WASP questionnaire takes less than 20 minutes and AMEA only a couple of minutes

Give it a try!